

A STUDY ON EMOTIONAL MATURITY OF HIGHER SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS OF DARJEELING

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Abstract

The study was designed to examine some of the factors regarding emotional maturity of higher secondary school students of government and private and rural and urban areas of Darjeeling district of West Bengal. The sample consists of 200 higher secondary school students selected randomly. The tool used for this study was Emotional maturity scale developed and Standardised by Yashvir Singh & Dr. Mahesh Bhargava, National Psychological Corporation, Agra.

Keywords: *Emotions, Emotional Maturity, Gender, Locality and Higher Secondary School*

Introduction:

Education system of any nation is a mirror through which the image of the nation being shaped and likely to be shaped can be seen. It is a process which the personal is continuously striving for greater sense of emotional health both intra-psychically and inter-personally. In the presents circumstances, youth as well as children are facing difficulties in life. Emotions have strong link with urges, need and interests. The emotions are a way of acting, as a way of getting along the world, they may be constructive and destructive. Emotional pressure is increasing day by day at adolescent stage. Emotionally matured person can make /better adjustment with himself as well as the others. Emotional maturity refers to that the stage of individual which the individual is able to face reality and deal with it, is interest in given receiving love, is able to learn from his experience and able to accept frustration and hostility in a constructive manner. **Ronald.E.Mcnairs** in his research on “learning pace of school children in regard to

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emotional maturity” found that students with a high level of dedication, commitment, desire and emotional maturity can make effective learning and learn as much as they want. **Peter Lichtenberg (2005)** in his research on “Emotional Maturity Across Life Span “found that man has ability to work with others who has emotional maturity and stability. He focussed on ageing as well as personality and emotional maturity across life span in his study. In the present circumstances, youth as well as children are facing difficulties in life. Generally, education conducted as a process or methods of learning and training that the whole of human personality in different dimension. Education enables man to draw out his hidden talents. **Dosanjh(1960)**, “Emotional maturity means balanced personality. It means ability to govern disturbing emotion, show steadiness and endurance under pressure and to be tolerant and free from neurotic tendency”. Emotional maturity is the ability to bear tension and it is the ability to develop high tolerance for disagree circumstance. Self concept is love and happy with whom you are now. It is an agreement with ourself to appreciate validates, accept and support who you are at every moment. **Morgan (1924)** stated the view that an adequate theory of emotional maturity must take an account of the full scope of the individual powers and his ability to enjoy the use of his powers. As emotion do play central role in the life of an individual, one is expected to have higher emotional maturity in order to lead an effective life. It is also true that our behaviour is constantly influenced by the emotional maturity level that we possess. Emotional maturity is a process in which their personality integrated. The process of the maturation and learning play effective roles in the maturation and emotion in human beings. Emotional maturity differs in each stage of growth and development i.e; from infancy to adulthood. The concept of maturity is used in psychology and psychiatry. High emotional maturity enables the individual to withstand the strains of life. **Bessel (2004)** viewed emotional maturity as those behavioural patterns that make good adjustments in life. An emotionally mature adolescent has the capacity to withstand the delay in satisfaction of needs. During this stage, emotions play an important role in determining future personality. Emotional maturity is the ability to bear tension and it is the ability to developed high tolerance for disagree circumstance. Emotional maturity is the capability to these challenges in a more balanced way. Emotional maturity refers to ability to express emotions in appropriate and balanced way. The emotional maturity is the key to a happy, fulfilled life. Without which, the individual falls as easy prey to the dependencies and insecurities. An emotionally mature child has the capability to make effective adjustment with himself, members of his family. His peers in the school, society and culture. A person may said to be emotionally matures if he has his possession

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almost all types of emotions-positive or negative and is able to express them at the appropriate time in an appropriate degree. Emotional maturity is a state of balanced feeling and self-control. Emotional maturity is a requirement for starting and maintaining relationships. It is a prerequisite for long term happiness. Emotional immaturity is associated with entanglements, transferences and unsatisfying shallow relationships. Career decisions are often based on emotions of happiness and affection or even fear, rather than what is rationally best for one's career. Emotional maturity is the ability to bear tension, showing indifference toward certain kinds of stimuli that affect the child or adolescent. We can say that emotional maturity portrays the ability to direct and channel our emotions, also assess others emotional state and influence their actions.

Concept of Emotions:

Etymologically, the word 'emotion' has derived from Latin word "Emovere" that means 'to stir up' or 'to excite'. Therefore, emotion refers to our mind and body as an agitated or excited state. These difficulties are giving rise to many psychosomatic problems such as anxiety, tensions, frustrations and emotional upsets in the day-to-day life. If they are satisfied, an individual is said to be enjoying a happy life and is emotionally stable. Woodworth (1945) defined Emotion as "a moved" or "stirred up" state of an organism. It is a stirred-up state of feelings that is the way it appears to the individual to the individual himself. It is a disturbed muscular and glandular activity that is the way it appears to an external observer." According to Hockenbury and Honkenbury (2007), "An emotion is a complex psychological state that involves three distinct components: a subjective experience, physiological response and a behavioural or experience response". Crow & Crow, "Emotion is an affective experience that accompanies generalized inner adjustment and mental and psychological stirred-up states in the individual and that shows itself in his overt behaviour." An emotionally mature person is one who is able to keep a lid on feelings. He can suffer in silence. He can bide his time in spite of present discomfort. He is not subject to swing in mood, he is not volatile. When he does express emotion, he does so with moderation, decently and in good order'. Emotions sometimes lead to disintegration of our actions. Emotions are the great motivating force throughout the span of human life; affecting aspirations, actions and thoughts of an individual. It is process of readjustment, which is patterned in accordance with the approved expression and repression in their culture. So, an emotionally mature person can have better adjustment with himself as well as others.

Emotional Maturity:

Emotional maturity is the ability to bear tension and it is the ability to develop high tolerance for disagree circumstances. Emotional maturity observed through thoughts and behaviours when a person faced with a difficult situation his level of emotional maturity is one of the biggest factors in determining his or her ability to cope. Emotional maturity is considered as the balance between the inner-outer emotional expressions of a person in different situations. Emotional maturity is not only the effective determinant of personality pattern but also helps to control the growth of individual development. The emotional maturity is the process of impulse control through the agency of 'self'. Emotional maturity is the outcome of healthy emotional development. Emotionally matured person is able to swings in moods and suffer in silence. When he express emotion, he express with moderation, decently and in good order. Emotion takes a vital role in these mental processes. Control of our emotion and understand others emotions make a personality of a human being. According to Hurlock, 'Emotional maturity involves the kind of living that most richly and fully expresses what a person has in him a level of his development'. According to Walter D.Smitson (1974), emotional maturity is "a process in which the personality is continually striving for greater sense of emotional health, both intra-psychically and intra personally."

Need of the Study:

Students are the backbone of the educational process. Education is a process and acts also as an instrument to bring out the innate behaviour of the individual. Emotional maturity is the ability to handle situations without unnecessarily escalating them. In the present era of modernization and globalization Emotional maturity is very much essential for the students to realize his/her potentialities and capabilities to face the challenges in life. To be emotionally mature is to acknowledge an emotion as it arises, and act accordingly. Instead of seeking to blame someone else for their problems or behaviour, emotionally mature people seek to fix the problem or behaviour. They accept accountability for their actions. Students can experience emotional responses and assumptions about their classmates and themselves. In the present circumstance, youth as well as children are facing difficulties in life. These difficulties are giving rise to many psychosomatic problems such as anxiety, tensions, frustrations and emotional upsets in the day-to-day life. Emotional maturity takes this idea further offering not only the ability to recognize one's own emotions, but also to access them in an empowering way. Actually, emotional maturity is not only the effective determine of personality pattern but it also helps to control the growth of adolescent's development. Most Higher Secondary

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Students are at emotional stage. The present study thus attempts to provide a clear picture on the emotional maturity of higher secondary school students of Darjeeling district of West Bengal.

Method and Sampling Frame

The secondary school students studying in Darjeeling district will constitute the competent of the study. The population of the present study constitute all the secondary school student studying in class 11 and 12 of Darjeeling. The study was conducted on a sample of 200 students (100 boys and 100 girls) studying in higher secondary school students situated in urban and rural areas especially from government & private schools in Darjeeling. The techniques were used random sampling and samples are collected only from the students of higher secondary level schools located in Darjeeling district, West Bengal.

Tools

Emotional Maturity Scale developed and Standardised by Yashvir Singh & Dr. Mahesh Bhargaa will be taken for as the tools of the study on the purpose of data collection. Emotional Maturity Scale of 48 items under the five categories: Emotional Stability, Emotional Progression, Social Adjustment, Personality Integration, Independence. EMS is a self-reporting five point scale. The items are so stated if the answer is in positive way (very much) score of 5 is given, for (much) 4 is given, for (undecided) 3, and for (probably) 2, and for negative answer of (never) a score of 1 is to be awarded. Therefore the higher the score on the scale, greater the degree of emotional maturity.

Objectives

1. To study the emotional maturity among rural and urban secondary school students.
2. To study the emotional maturity among male and female students.
3. To study emotional maturity among private and government secondary school.

Hypothesis

1. There is no significant difference between the emotional maturity among rural and urban secondary school students.
2. There is no significant difference between the emotional maturity among male and female students.
3. There is no significant difference between the emotional maturity among private and government secondary school students.

Findings and Data Analysis

The data may be adequate, valid and reliable to any extent, it does not serve any worthwhile purpose unless it is carefully edited, systematically classified and tabulated, scientifically analyses, intelligently interpreted and rationally concluded.

The details of the analysis of data collected from the selected sample on 'title' are given in the following tables.

Hypothesis: There is no significant difference between the emotional maturity among male and female students.

Table 3.1: Comparison across Gender on Emotional Maturity of Secondary School Students

Emotional Maturity	Gender	Mean	SD	t-test
	Girls	132.64	32.80	1.783@
	Boys	125.05	25.51	

@Not significant

There is no significant difference in emotional maturity of secondary school students therefore null hypothesis: '*There is no significant difference between the emotional maturity among male and female students*' is accepted. *It can be understood that there is no difference in the Emotional Maturity among the Secondary School Students with respect to Gender.*

Hypothesis: There is no significant difference between emotional maturity among private and government secondary school students.

Table 3.2: Comparison across Management on Emotional Maturity of Secondary School Students

Emotional Maturity	Management	Mean	SD	t-test
	Private	124.52	26.16	2.293*
	Government	134.15	32.85	

*Significant @ 0.05 level

There is a significant difference between private and government secondary school students regarding emotional maturity therefore null hypothesis: '*There is no significant difference between emotional maturity among private and government secondary school students*' is rejected. It can be understood that there is a highly significant difference in the Emotional Maturity among the secondary school students with respect to management.

Hypothesis: There is no significant difference between the emotional maturity among rural and urban secondary school students.

Table 3.3: Comparison across Locality on Emotional Maturity of Secondary School Students

	Locality	Mean	SD	t-test
Emotional Maturity	Urban	136.50	33.515	3.468**
	Rural	122.17	24.163	

**Significant@0.01 level

There is a significant difference between urban and rural secondary school students regarding emotional maturity at 0.01 levels therefore the null hypothesis: 'There is no significant difference between the emotional maturity among rural and urban secondary school students' is rejected. It can be understood that Emotional Maturity of Secondary School Students with respect to Locality is highly significant.

Findings

No significant difference was found in emotional maturity in higher secondary school students in relation to type of schools (Government and Private school) and gender (boys and girls). So, to be concluded, students of private and government schools are similar in the emotional maturity.

1. There was no significant difference in emotional maturity of higher secondary school students with respect to their gender.
2. There was a significant difference in emotional maturity of higher secondary school students with respect to their locality of school.
3. There was a significant difference between emotional maturity of government and private secondary school students.

Conclusions and Suggestions

Emotional Maturity is the effective determinant of personality pattern as well it also helps to control the growth of the adolescent's development. The investigator found that there is no significant difference between emotional maturity of higher secondary school students with respect to gender. The study revealed a significant difference in emotional maturity of higher secondary school students with respect to their locality (rural and urban) and type of school management (government and private)

The study will help to understand the level of emotional maturity of both rural and urban students. It will also help the students to understand and cope up with their emotional problems. It will also help the policy makers to take care of emotional state of students while planning the curriculum. It will help in directing the school administration to develop activities for students to develop emotional responsibilities in their day-to-day life. Teachers can help to progress emotional maturity among school students by providing them different learning ambiances.

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